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ENSURING COMPETITIVE ADVANTAGES IN THE FIELD OF FORMULATION OF THE ASSORTMENT POLICY OF HOTEL AND RESTAURANT BUSINESS ENTERPRISES

**JEL Classification: L83, M31, M11
SECTION “ECONOMICS”: Економіка**

Annotation. The prerequisites for the formation and the specific impact of assortment policy on ensuring the competitive advantages of hotel and restaurant enterprises have been generalized. The dynamic nature of achieving competitive advantages through the development of an assortment strategy in the hospitality industry has been substantiated. The properties of the relationship between assortment formation and the development of the strategic set components of hotel and restaurant enterprises have been identified. This study explores the key aspects of assortment strategy in the hospitality industry. The peculiarities of the development and implementation of assortment policy at different stages of the competitive advantage life cycle in the hotel and restaurant business have been established. The substantive characteristics have been formulated, and the specifics of building structural and functional alternatives for assortment management organization in hotel and restaurant enterprises have been determined. The role and significance of the product marketing program in ensuring competitive advantages in the field of assortment policy formation for hotel and restaurant enterprises have been identified. The content of managerial tasks related to the formation of a diversified assortment set for hotel and restaurant enterprises has been established. The adaptive nature of the process of ensuring competitive advantages in the field of assortment policy formation for hotel and

restaurant enterprises has been revealed, including the ability to adapt to changing business conditions, mobility, high adaptability to the context of market competition, and the "flexibility" of internal structures that determine a high level of adaptation.

Keywords: competition, competitive advantages, assortment, assortment policy, marketing, enterprise strategy, hotel and restaurant business enterprise.

Анотація. Узагальнено передумови формування та особливості впливу асортиментної політики на забезпечення конкурентних переваг підприємств готельно-ресторанного бізнесу. Доведено динамічний характер забезпечення конкурентних переваг в сфері формування асортиментної політики підприємств готельно-ресторанного бізнесу. Визначено властивості зв'язку між формуванням асортименту та розробкою складових стратегічного набору підприємств готельно-ресторанного бізнесу. Розкрито зміст асортиментної політики підприємств готельно-ресторанного бізнесу. Встановлено особливості розробки та реалізації асортиментної політики підприємств готельно-ресторанного господарства на різних етапах життєвого циклу конкурентних переваг бізнесу. Сформовано змістовні характеристики та визначено особливості побудови структурно-функціональних альтернатив організації управління асортиментом підприємств готельно-ресторанного бізнесу. Визначено роль та значення маркетингової програми при забезпеченні конкурентних переваг в сфері формування асортиментної політики підприємств готельно-ресторанного бізнесу. Встановлено зміст управлінських завдань щодо формування диверсифікованого асортиментного набору підприємств готельно-ресторанного бізнесу. Розкрито адаптивний характер процесу забезпечення конкурентних переваг в сфері формування асортиментної політики підприємств готельно-ресторанного бізнесу (здатність адаптуватися до змін умов діяльності; мобільність, висока пристосованість до контексту ринкового суперництва; «еластичність» внутрішніх структур, що визначають високий рівень цієї адаптації).

Ключові слова: конкуренція, конкурентні переваги, асортимент, асортиментна політика, маркетинг, стратегія підприємства, підприємство готельно-ресторанного бізнесу.

Introduction

Problem statement and its connection with important scientific and practical tasks. The steady increase in the requirements for the quality of managerial decisions that determine the actions of an enterprise in both the strategic perspective of development and the current economic situation is driven by the significant complexity of economic and business-related tasks faced by enterprises. Due to the continuous changes in business conditions, enterprises encounter the challenge of selecting the optimal development path from several alternatives to achieve their set objectives.

Therefore, a necessary prerequisite for strengthening the competitiveness of an enterprise—based on a comprehensive market analysis and an assessment of its internal resources—is the meticulous development of action plans across various areas of enterprise activity, including scientific and technological, assortment, technological, sales, pricing, personnel, and resource components of its economic strategy. In this context, the key element in studying the problems associated with implementing a combination of strategic and current plans is the assortment policy, which establishes the fundamental principles for developing the mechanism of interaction between the producer and consumers.

Thus, the impact of assortment policy on the formation of final business outcomes and competitive advantages is extensive and significant, underscoring the relevance of a thorough examination of the competitive aspects of structuring the assortment of products and services offered by a business entity.

Analysis of research and publications. The issue of marketing support for competitive advantages in the formation of an enterprise's assortment policy has been extensively examined in the works of many

prominent scholars, including V. Bilozubenko [3], A. Boichuk [1], D. Vega [9], N. Wilner [9], F. Wiersema [8], O. Gokhberg [3], M. Kizym [2], S. Kingsnorth [4], P. Kotler [5], Ye. Krykavskiy [6], K. Lane [5], M. Mavrina [7], A. Pylypenko [2], O. Pokhilchenko [6], D. Smolarski [9], M. Treacy [8], O. Chernega [3], I. Yaldin [2], and others. However, certain aspects, particularly those related to the competitive dimensions of assortment policy formation in the hotel and restaurant business, remain insufficiently explored and require a more in-depth examination.

The purpose of the article. This study aims to generalize the theoretical foundations and develop recommendations for ensuring competitive advantages in the formation of assortment policy in the hotel and restaurant business.

The results

Assortment policy involves the implementation of certain targeted actions by the enterprise management, aimed at satisfying the identified solvent demand of target consumer groups (within relevant market segments), through which the effective formation of the nomenclature and assortment of goods and the planned sales volumes are ensured. Assortment policy, implemented at various levels of enterprise management, includes both strategic resolution of the issue of selecting the product nomenclature to be produced and tactical decisions regarding the operational optimization of the product offer composition, which is particularly important for business entities operating in a multifunctional sphere, such as the hotel and restaurant industry.

An enterprise must pursue such an assortment policy that is aimed at regularly updating the assortment to best meet potential consumer needs, but at the same time, it should be based on the previous assortment to minimize costs associated with such renewal. Thus, the assortment policy of a hotel and restaurant business enterprise represents a dynamic system that is constantly evolving, and the patterns of its development must be considered in the context of assortment renewal in response to changing market demands.

The formation of assortment policy in hotel and restaurant enterprises is carried out considering a number of factors. In this regard, in the context of structuring the assortment of a hotel and restaurant business enterprise, it is important to address the following tasks: determining the real and anticipated needs for certain goods and services (taking into account the complementary mutual influence of individual assortment positions); identifying the optimal option for structuring the nomenclature and assortment of a multifunctional business; identifying sources of product resources necessary for the formation of such an assortment; assessing the material capabilities of the enterprise for the production, distribution, and/or sale of individual products in the context of and considering the variability of consumer demand; and determining the main directions of innovative assortment renewal.

The goal of a hotel and restaurant business enterprise in the field of assortment is to form a real or forecasted assortment that embodies existing or potential technological and material capabilities in products that, while bringing profit to the producer, are defined by consumer value that satisfies the buyer.

To form an optimal assortment, well-thought-out, continuous managerial influences are necessary, selecting various directions that correspond to the current state of the internal and external environment of the enterprise. Thus, assortment management of an enterprise is the process of choosing the optimal direction for changing the structure of the assortment. However, it should be noted that scholars from various economic fields are actively working on the issue of forming an optimal assortment, considering assortment policy from different perspectives.

Marketers, being more market-oriented than focused on the production process, prioritize demand and the production capabilities of the enterprise for the release of new products in their research on assortment policy, without emphasizing the issue of optimizing the existing assortment. Although the field of marketing does address the profitability of the product offering as well as the overall activities of the enterprise, this aspect remains insufficiently explored due to the specific nature of the marketing approach. For management, and particularly for financial management as one of its components, the approach to assortment policy is

characteristic as a set of measures aimed at optimizing financial resources from the perspective of the profitability of produced goods and cost minimization.

Thus, based on the analysis of the development of approaches to the formation of assortment policy and the important role it plays in the efficiency of an enterprise's operations under modern market conditions, it can be concluded that two methodological approaches to implementing an enterprise's assortment policy have been established: the marketing approach and the financial approach.

A critical aspect of the marketing approach to product assortment management in the hospitality industry is considering the impact of the business and product lifecycle. The concept of the life cycle describes the dynamics of changes in the market position (primarily competitive advantages) of a certain object from its inception to its eventual disappearance. The periods that constitute the market life of an object (a product or an organization) form the stages of the life cycle, and therefore, different products, united by a common marketing orientation toward meeting the needs of clients in hotel and restaurant services, have different durations of the life cycle and each of its stages. The issue of developing and implementing assortment policy in the context of the dynamics of the life cycle is of primary importance for an enterprise at all times, regardless of its economic condition (under favorable market conditions, the assortment expands, while under unfavorable conditions, it contracts), which makes this area extremely important and one that requires constant attention.

Thus, the goal of forming the assortment policy of a hotel and restaurant business enterprise can be defined as managing the formation and production of a competitive assortment within specified timeframes, maintaining the optimality of the already produced assortment, that is, ensuring profit maximization and removing non-competitive types of products from the assortment set while taking into account the sector-specific characteristics of demand formation for the relevant goods and services.

The implementation of this goal is inextricably linked to the need to ensure fundamental requirements for the assortment management system of a hotel and restaurant business enterprise, namely: the ability to adapt to changes in market conditions; mobility, high adaptability to changing internal and external operating conditions; "flexibility" of internal structures, which determine a high level of this adaptation, and others.

The next stage in the formation of the mechanism for developing and implementing assortment policy should be considered the development of an organizational management structure, the main principle of which is the application of an approach based on the use of strategic marketing methods (which makes it possible to ensure the implementation of the strategy, the interaction of management with the external environment, and ultimately, the effective resolution of the task of forming an optimal assortment to maintain sustainable competitive advantages). At the same time, it should be taken into account that entering the market with a competitive assortment represents only one component of a hotel and restaurant business enterprise's work on its released assortment.

After gaining a foothold in the market, the key element of managerial activity in assortment management is a set of measures aimed at the systematic improvement and renewal of the composition of the product offering, including the identification of cost-reduction reserves, modification of the combination of elements in a multifunctional product offering, research into the adaptability of products and services to demand fluctuations, and others.

Since two distinct types of tasks—operational and strategic—are clearly traced in the structuring of the assortment of a hotel and restaurant business enterprise, it seems appropriate to develop a management system in this area along the following main directions: the introduction of a dual management system as a distinction between operational and strategic management systems, that is, the management and control of strategic projects (market research and new product development) should be separated from the production management system (actions aimed at cost reduction and the formation of an optimal assortment); maintaining the orientation of the management system toward solving strategic tasks, concentrating the efforts of top management on defining the assortment concept; establishing closer relationships between the marketing department and the units responsible for product and service modernization, creating new

packaging, and similar activities based on marketing research; transitioning to greater openness toward the external environment (combining the production process with continuous marketing analysis).

Thus, the development and implementation of an assortment policy in a hotel and restaurant business enterprise must be carried out comprehensively, based on the combination of the assortment concept and strategy defined in one division and short-term tactical programs developed in another. The targeted assortment policy of a hotel and restaurant business enterprise consists of establishing such an assortment structure that enables the enterprise to secure a certain market share, achieve the planned profit volume, and address other operational and strategic objectives. At the same time, management must be prepared from the implementation stage for the necessity of eventually phasing out certain products from the assortment. Consequently, within the assortment structure, new types of products must be developed, making the product life cycle concept particularly significant in this context. Compliance with the requirements of orientation toward the stages of the life cycle of elements of the product offering necessitates analyzing the enterprise's activities not only from the perspective of the present but also in terms of its future development, creating the need for systematic work on planning and mastering new products. Therefore, it appears necessary at the planning stage of a new product to establish a criterion (or criteria) for the feasibility of its sale: a specified level of profitability, sales volume, or profit amount, which will subsequently allow for a decision on discontinuing the product. Additionally, an exit plan for this product from the market should be developed, including a schedule for the gradual or abrupt cessation of production and sales, restructuring of the enterprise and reallocation of resources, reorganization of distribution channels, and intensification of sales promotion tools. Operational assortment policy involves addressing the issue of selecting the nomenclature of products to be produced and its optimization, as well as determining an economically justified production program in terms of volume and assortment.

The conducted analysis of various existing types of marketing service organization allows concluding that the most effective management of operational assortment policy in a hotel and restaurant business enterprise corresponds to a divisional structure of the marketing department. The advantage of such a structure lies in the ability to personalize responsibility for decision-making regarding the production and sale of specific products or product groups, that is, applying a product-based organization of the department, where an employee in the operational marketing control and planning unit is assigned one or several products. Their responsibilities should include overseeing the implementation of all functions related to assortment management, with the right to report directly to the marketing director in case of significant deviations in the management process. The employee must ensure that the information collection and marketing research department conducts timely and high-quality market monitoring of this product, assesses its strengths and weaknesses in comparison with competing products, and that the new product development department does not delay rationalization proposals for improving the product and promptly implements them in production.

At each stage of the product life cycle, specific challenges arise in promoting the product on the market, so marketing programs and related expenses must take into account the specifics of individual phases of the life cycle. For example, when a product reaches the saturation stage, alongside strict cost control for this product, preparations should begin for a gradual phase-out program so that it can be applied at the onset of the decline phase.

The primary objective of an operational marketing program in the field of assortment policy for the hotel and restaurant business is to determine the volume of production of goods and services (considering their mutual complementarity) for the current period.

The main task of developing and implementing an assortment policy based on an operational marketing program is to comprehensively identify those types of products and services whose combination can ensure the highest level of profitability for a hotel and restaurant business enterprise and to orient production toward the release of such products. Given the significant complexity of this task due to the multitude of diverse factors influencing profitability and their complex interrelations, decisions are typically made based on a multi-variant analysis, which should include several alternative prospective options for

forming the produced assortment, so that there is a basis for establishing feedback between sales and production: if for some reason one assortment option is unsatisfactory, the enterprise should transition to another option. In general, this sequence of actions reflects the process of managing an enterprise's assortment policy: selecting an optimal decision from a set of alternatives based on a certain criterion.

Conclusions

The assortment policy of a hotel and restaurant business enterprise represents a dynamic system that is constantly evolving, and the patterns of its development should be considered in the context of assortment renewal in response to changing market demands. A key aspect of implementing the marketing approach to structuring the assortment of products and services in a multifunctional business within the hotel and restaurant service sector is taking into account the impact of the business life cycle as a whole and that of individual products in particular. The targeted assortment policy of a hotel and restaurant business enterprise involves establishing such an assortment structure that enables the enterprise to secure a certain market share, achieve the planned profit volume, and address other operational and strategic objectives.

In the context of structuring the assortment of a hotel and restaurant business enterprise, it is important to address the following tasks: determining real and anticipated needs for certain goods and services (considering the complementary mutual influence of individual assortment positions); identifying the optimal structure of the nomenclature and assortment for a multifunctional business; identifying sources of product resources necessary for forming such an assortment; assessing the material capabilities of the enterprise for the production, distribution, and/or sale of individual products in the context of and considering the variability of consumer demand; and defining the main directions for innovative assortment renewal.

Further research in this field will be related to the improvement of methodological aspects for assessing the competitiveness of the assortment positions of hotel and restaurant business enterprises.

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